

The Effects of British Council Training Program English as Medium of Instruction on Primary School Teachers in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

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Abstract

The present study would lead to know the effects of British Council training program on the primary school teachers in Khyber Pukhtunkhawa. The objective of the study was to know the effects of the training program on the primary school teachers. The primary school teachers, who successfully completed grade III training English as Medium of Instruction in Khyber Pukhtunkhawa, were the population of the study. The study was delimited to male primary school teachers of the three districts namely Mardan, Peshawar and Swabi. The target population was 1947 male primary school teachers, of whom 330 was selected. The data was collected through questionnaire and analyzed through percentage and chi-square. The results of the study that the primary school teachers were able to use English as Medium of Instruction. The study recommended that such trainings should be arranged for teachers to improve their skills of using English as Medium of Instruction.

Key Words:

British Council, Primary School Teachers, English as Medium of Instruction, Activity Based Teaching and Students Centered Teaching

Introduction

The collection of all those planning and policies that are made to train teachers in contents, attitude and skills necessary for their job is called teachers' education. According to S.M. Shahid (2007) teacher education does not only mean how to teach but make teachers dynamic and innovative in their approach to teaching. Trainee teachers learnt how to get maximum results through minimum use of energy, time and resources. Similarly, Bennet (2000) the modern world teacher needs to be dynamic because due to technology everything is changing rapidly. Teacher must be trained to be scientific and logical in thinking and sympathetic towards the students.

English has become a global language in the last twenty to thirty year and it has dominated the world market in general and the linguistic side in particular. Education is also one of the sectors affected heavily by this trend. English as Medium of Instruction is a burning issue for the world's leaders in non-English speaking countries in post-colonial world in Asia because it is a direct threat to their culture and society (Tsui, 2004).

The KP government shows its interest in teachers' professional development which will ultimately improve the whole system of education. For the above mentioned propose the Elementary and Secondary Education Department (ESED) Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and British Council Pakistan signed a Memorandum of Understanding to improve the quality of teaching and practices of all primary school teachers of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Literature Review

English language teaching faced many challenges in the past and even now also. Changes are accruing in English language teaching continuously to adopt the teaching style to the changing circumstances (Willis and Willis, 1996). The most important challenge in the present situation is found, recruit and train enough language teachers to teach effectively to the students and make them capable to survive in the global environment (Tribble, 2012). The governments all over the world are facing problems because the numbers of students are increasing rapidly in the international market.

This rapid increase in the number of students who wanted to learn English forced the governments to induct teachers who are trained to teach their students effectively (Boix et al., 2011; Wedell, 2009). Internationally, a large number of students start to learn English at primary level. Their working hours to learn English increased when they take admission in high schools. In many cases, it is observed that these students continue their journey of learning English in Universities also and particularly in those countries where signs of internationalization are evident in their education. English is becoming the communication tool of the world and this scenario suggests that many teachers needed to fulfill the needs of the students in these countries (Graddol, 2006; Gimenez, 2009). This scenario created a shortage of English Language teachers which need an urgent solution.

English as medium of instruction had a problematic nature therefore many countries of the world made effective policies but still there are many which do not have policies. Those countries which do not have policies for English were more flexible towards the medium of instruction. They changed their policies according to their academic, political and social needs. As a result, a lot of differences are found in the quality of teachers in those countries (Barduhn & Johnson, 2009). Similarly, if quality teachers are recruited and trained accordingly but still there is an issue that some of the very good teachers may quit the job. A lot of researches had been done on the same issue (Coombe & Barlow, 2007; British Council, 2015), but still there are areas that need research to reach a conclusion, especially the methods of recruiting teachers, professional trainings and the policy how to retain competent and professionally trained language teachers.

A system using English as a medium of instruction inside the classrooms is called English Medium Education. Manivannan (2006) explained that English had many functions and used in many fields. For many occupations and profession knowledge of English is must and compulsory therefore many countries of the world made English as medium of instruction as an integral part of their curriculum and institutions (Muhammad, 2009). The problem related to medium of instruction is the most controversial and has a historical background as well (Mahboob, 2003).

Baloch (2003) said that the teachers' competencies in speaking and using English for instruction is directly linked therefore it is important to consider both making policy for English language teaching. Tahir (2007) discussed the problems of teachers and found that in the present situation in Pakistan the teachers are not in a position to use English as medium in the whole class due to lack of competency in speaking English. Similarly, Mansoor (2005) stated some problems like controlling language first during instruction, adopting new language habits, pronunciation issues and problem of accurate translation of language related to English medium instruction in teaching.

Listening, speaking, reading and writing are the four basic skills necessary for learning a language (Bel & Luis, 2010). Shamim (2008) observed that the general assumption about teachers is that some teachers are competent in reading and writing but weak in the use of listening and speaking and vice versa. Furthermore, those teachers who have good communicative skills are liked by their students. They are followed as role model and competent teachers have more students. The teachers' competency in speaking makes his students also fluent in speaking (Maley, 2009).

Coleman (2010) stated that language experts have common opinion about the four basic aims of language teaching which are: ability to speak fluently, listen, write and read. Velasquez and Ocampo (2003) said that usually our teachers as well as our students do not get the chance to speak inside and outside the class. Our examination system mostly focused writing skills of students and speaking is not included in it. A lot of practice and attention is required for speaking fluently. The teachers should use the natural way for learning a language to speak which is listening and repeating the language. We all used the above-mentioned method while learning our mother tongue (Cantoni, 2007). Mueen (1993) observed that another cause of ignoring the competencies of listening and speaking in Pakistan is that the teachers themselves are the product of the traditional systems and they are not competent in speaking English or teaching and speaking in their classes. The shy and conservative teachers tried hard to speak confidently. The hard work makes their teaching better and they are able to teach language effectively. Pronunciation and grammar are essential for language teaching without these two, it will be difficult to teach effectively and accurately (Fiorito, 2005).

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To know the effectiveness of the training program for primary school teachers in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Hypothesis of the Study

- H0-1 There is no significant relationship between the effects of the training and primary school teachers' performance.

Research Methodology

The nature of this study is descriptive and the type is quantitative. The present study evaluates the role of British Council program training program English as a Medium of Instructions for the primary school teachers in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Population of the Study

The population of the study is the 24000 (Annual School Statistics, 2017) primary school teachers who complete grade III training under the British Council training program English as Medium of Instruction in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Due to the financial and cultural constraints the study is delimited to three districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa namely Mardan, Peshawar and Swabi. The target population is 1947 male primary school teachers of district Mardan, Peshawar and Swabi who successfully completed their training under grade III training program of British Council in using English as Medium of Instruction in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (Annual School Statistics, 2017-18). So, 1947 male primary school teachers were the target population for this study.

In district Mardan 802, Peshawar 583 and Swabi 562 teachers successfully completed grade III training *English as Medium of Instruction* in 2017. The sample size of the above population is 330 according to L.R. Gay (1996). One hundred and ten primary school teachers from each district were selected and the questionnaires were filled by them. A close ended and self-developed questionnaire was developed on five Likert scale ranging from strongly agreed to disagree and it was finalized after consultation with the supervisor. The questionnaire includes fifty items, ten items each on the five objectives of the study.

Data and Data Collection

The researcher firstly received the permission letter from the university and DEOs of the concerned districts. Then personally visited to the selected schools of the districts Mardan, Peshawar and Swabi and filled the questionnaires by three hundred and thirty (330) primary school teachers (one hundred and ten from each district) who completed grade III training English as Medium of Instruction under the British Council.

The data was collected through a five Likert scale self-made questionnaire from primary school teachers of district Mardan, Peshawar and Swabi who complete grade III training under British Council. The collected data was first fed into SPSS version 16 and then it was analyzed through percentage and Chi-Square test. The analyzed data was put into tables item by item and then it was interpreted below in the tables.

Results

Table 1. I managed my Lesson Effectively After the Training.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Table value	Residual	Chi-Square value (χ^2)
SA	100	30.3	30.3	Table value	34.0	492.33
A	210	63.6	93.9	9.49	144.0	(df) 4
UD	7	2.1	96.1		-59.0	
SDA	2	.6	96.7		-64.0	
DA	11	3.3	100.0		-55.0	
Total	330	100.0				

One hundred (100) primary school teachers strongly agreed and two hundred and ten (210) agreed with cumulative percent of 93.9 which shows that majority of the primary school teachers either agreed or strongly agreed that they managed their lesson effectively after the training. Comparatively, primary school teachers who strongly disagreed are two (02) and eleven (11) teachers disagreed with cumulative percent of 2.7 while twenty-seven (07) primary school teachers are undecided about the statement with cumulative percent of 2.1. The result is strongly supported by Chi-square value 492.33 which is much greater than the t-value (9.49) at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 2. It Helped me to Teach my Topic Properly.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Table value	Residual	Chi-Square value (χ^2)
SA	96	29.1	29.1	9.49	30.0	518.57
A	216	65.5	94.5		150.0	(df) 4
UD	10	3.0	97.6		-56.0	
SDA	5	1.5	99.1		-61.0	

DA	3	.9	100.0	-63.0
Total	330	100.0		

Ninety-six (96) primary school teachers strongly agreed and two hundred and sixteen (216) agreed with cumulative percent of 94.5 which shows that majority of the primary school teachers either agreed or strongly agreed that the training helped them to teach their topics properly. Comparatively, primary school teachers who strongly disagreed are five (05) and three (03) teachers disagreed with cumulative percent of 2.4 while ten (10) primary school teachers are undecided about the statement with cumulative percent of 3.0. The result is strongly supported by Chi-square value 518.57 which is much greater than the t-value (9.49) at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 3. I Involved My Students More in the Teaching Learning Process After the Training.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Table value	Residual	Chi-Square value (χ^2)
SA	133	40.3	40.3	9.49	67.0	431.15
A	180	54.5	94.8		114.0	(df) 4
UD	11	3.3	98.2		-55.0	
SDA	1	.3	98.5		-65.0	
DA	5	1.5	100.0		-61.0	
Total	330	100.0				

One hundred and thirty-three (133) primary school teachers strongly agreed and one hundred and eighty (180) agreed with cumulative percent of 94.8 which shows that majority of the primary school teachers either agreed or strongly agreed that after the training they involved their students more in the teaching learning process. Comparatively, primary school teachers who strongly disagreed are one (01) and five (05) teachers disagreed with cumulative percent of 2.8 while eleven (11) primary school teachers are undecided about the statement with cumulative percent of 3.3. The result is strongly supported by Chi-square value 431.15 which is much greater than the t-value (9.49) at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 4. The Training Helped me to Arrange Different Activities in My Class Effectively.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Table value	Residual	Chi-Square value (χ^2)
SA	119	36.1	36.1	9.49	53.0	386.30
A	181	54.8	90.9		115.0	(df) 4
UD	16	4.8	95.8		-50.0	
SDA	7	2.1	97.9		-59.0	
DA	7	2.1	100.0		-59.0	
Total	330	100.0				

One hundred and eighteen (119) primary school teachers strongly agreed and one hundred and eight one (181) agreed with cumulative percent of 90.9 which shows that majority of the primary school teachers either agreed or strongly agreed that the training helped them to arrange different activities in their classes. Comparatively, primary school teachers who strongly disagreed are seven (07) and seven (07) teachers disagreed with cumulative percent of 4.2 while sixteen (16) primary school teachers are undecided about the statement with cumulative percent of 4.8. The result is strongly supported by Chi-square value 386.30 which is much greater than the t-value (9.49) at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 5. It Helped me to Deal with Individual Differences Effectively.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Table value	Residual	Chi-Square value (χ^2)
SA	99	30.0	30.0	9.49	33.0	258.48
A	165	50.0	80.0		99.0	(df) 4
UD	37	11.2	91.2		-29.0	
SDA	11	3.3	94.5		-55.0	
DA	18	5.5	100.0		-48.0	
Total	330	100.0				

Ninety-nine (99) primary school teachers strongly agreed and one hundred and sixty-five (165) agreed with

cumulative percent of 80.0 which shows that majority of the primary school teachers either agreed or strongly agreed that the training helped them to deal individual differences effectively among their students. Comparatively, primary school teachers who strongly disagreed are eleven (11) and eighteen (18) teachers disagreed with cumulative percent of 8.8 while thirty-seven (37) primary school teachers are undecided about the statement with cumulative percent of 11.2. The result is strongly supported by Chi-square value 258.48 which is much greater than the t-value (9.49) at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 6. I Included Materials for all Type of Learners in my Lesson After the Training.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Table value	Residual	Chi-Square value (χ^2)
SA	97	29.4	29.4	9.49	31.0	307.48
A	177	53.6	83.0		111.0	(df) 4
UD	31	9.4	92.4		-35.0	
SDA	8	2.4	94.8		-58.0	
DA	17	5.2	100.0		-49.0	
Total	330	100.0				

Ninety-seven (97) primary school teachers strongly agreed and one seventy-seven (177) primary school teachers agreed with cumulative percent of 83.0 which shows that majority of the primary school teachers either agreed or strongly agreed that after the training they include materials for all type of learners in their lesson. Comparatively, primary school teachers who strongly disagreed are eight (08) and seventeen (17) teachers disagreed with cumulative percent of 7.6 while thirty-one (31) primary school teachers are undecided about the statement with cumulative percent of 9.4. The result is strongly supported by Chi-square value 307.48 which is much greater than the t-value (9.49) at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 7. It Helped me to Teach Pronunciation Effectively.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Table value	Residual	Chi-Square value (χ^2)
SA	125	37.9	37.9	9.49	59.0	385.90
A	177	53.6	91.5		111.0	(df) 4
UD	8	2.4	93.9		-58.0	
SDA	6	1.8	95.8		-60.0	
DA	14	4.2	100.0		-52.0	
Total	330	100.0				

One hundred and twenty five (125) primary school teachers strongly agreed and one hundred and seventy seven (177) agreed with cumulative percent of 91.5 which shows that majority of the primary school teachers either agreed or strongly agreed that the training helped them to teach pronunciation effectively in their classes. Comparatively, primary school teachers who strongly disagreed are six (06) and fourteen (14) teachers disagreed with cumulative percent of 6.0 while eight (08) primary school teachers are undecided about the statement with cumulative percent of 2.4. The result is strongly supported by Chi-square value 385.90 which is much greater than the t-value (9.49) at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 8. I Used Different Methods to keep the Students Interested After the Training.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Table value	Residual	Chi-Square value (χ^2)
SA	142	43.0	43.0	9.49	76.0	430.69
A	173	52.4	95.5		107.0	(df) 4
UD	10	3.0	98.5		-56.0	
SDA	3	.9	99.4		-63.0	
DA	2	.6	100.0		64.0	
Total	330	100.0				

One hundred and forty two (142) primary school teachers strongly agreed and one hundred and seventy three (173) agreed with cumulative percent of 95.5 which shows that majority of they primary school teachers either agreed or strongly agreed that after the training they used different methods to keep the students interested in their classes. Comparatively, primary school teachers who strongly disagreed are three (03) and two (02) teachers disagreed with cumulative percent of 1.5 while eight (08) primary school teachers are undecided

about the statement with cumulative percent of 3.0. The result is strongly supported by Chi-square value 430.69 which is much greater than the t-value (9.49) at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 9. It Helped Me to Guide my Students to Learn Freely.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Table value	Residual	Chi-Square value (χ^2)
SA	126	38.2	38.2	9.49	60.0	392.75
A	177	53.6	91.8		111.0	(df) 4
UD	22	6.7	98.5		-44.0	
SDA	3	.9	99.4		-63.0	
DA	2	.6	100.0		-64.0	
Total	330	100.0				

One hundred and twenty-six (126) primary school teachers strongly agreed and one hundred and seventy-seven (177) agreed with cumulative percent of 91.8 which shows that majority of the primary school teachers either agreed or strongly agreed that the training helped them to guide their students to learn freely in their classes. Comparatively, primary school teachers who strongly disagreed are three (03) and two (02) teachers disagreed with cumulative percent of 1.5 while twenty-two (22) primary school teachers are undecided about the statement with cumulative percent of 6.7. The result is strongly supported by Chi-square value 392.75 which is much greater than the t-value (9.49) at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 10. I used the Classroom Language Effectively After the Training in my Class.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Table value	Residual	Chi-Square value (χ^2)
SA	137	41.5	41.5	9.49	71.0	340.30
A	158	47.9	89.4		92.0	(df) 4
UD	19	5.8	95.2		-47.0	
SDA	5	1.5	96.7		-61.0	
DA	11	3.3	100.0		-55.0	
Total	330	100.0				

One hundred and thirty-seven (137) primary school teachers strongly agreed and one hundred and fifty-eight (158) agreed with cumulative of 89.4 which show that majority of the primary school teachers either agreed or strongly agreed that after the training they used classroom language effectively in their classes. Comparatively, primary school teachers who strongly disagreed are five (05) and eleven (11) teachers disagreed with cumulative percent of 4.8 while twenty nineteen (19) primary school teachers are undecided about the statement with cumulative percent of 5.8. The result is strongly supported by Chi-square value 340.30 which is much greater than the t-value (9.49) at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The effectiveness level of the training was very high and it helped the trainees to manage their classes effectively, teach the topic more properly, to involve the students in academic learning increased after the training, to deal individual differences effectively, to include materials for all type of learners and teach pronunciation efficiently. After the training the trainees used different methods to make the students interested, guide students to learn freely and used classroom language effectively in their classes.

The environment of training centers had its effects on the trainings. If the environment is suitable for training then the training program will achieve its targeted objectives. Therefore, the government should provide proper training centers with suitable training environment for trainings. The qualified and professional trained master trainers are integral for an effective training program. The government should make sure that properly trained and expert trainers are arranged for all in-service training programs. The government spends a large amount of money on all the in-service training programs. Therefore, the department should select those teachers who have the required qualification and motivation to learn and use the time properly.

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